

Leveraging Open Data to Predict Property Price

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Summary

This work describes how open data sources were geospatially linked to create a machine learning model that predicts property prices in England and Wales. The model achieves an average error of 11.4% for a single property, and this error comes down to 0.3% for the total value of a sample of 500 properties.

KEYWORDS: Machine Learning, Geodemographics, Open Data, Regression

Background

Many studies have been conducted about predicting property price, specifically; using a hedonic model with Bayesian modelling (Clapp, Kim, Gelfand, 2003), regression with nearest neighbour residuals as input (Bourassa, Cantoni, Hoesli, 2010), and recently using boosted trees to predict prices (Manasa, Gupta, Narahari, 2020). One notion unites these studies: they focus on localised areas. This is where our work differs, as we leverage a larger, national dataset that captures variation that locally appears highly individual but nationally is more commonplace.

1.1. Method

Initially, a set of hypotheses was created for testing. This could then be used to justify the choice of input variables in a predictive model. Each of the hypotheses were grouped into four categories, each with a basis in the literature:

- Census statistics and geodemographics (Parker, Uprichard, Burrows, 2007; Harris, Sleight, Webber, 2005)
- Spatial dependency (Brunsdon, Fotheringham, Charlton, 2002),
- Crime (Lynch & Rasmussen, 2010)
- Temporal variation (Gupta & Miller, 2010).

We quantified the extent to which each factor affects prices: weighing the evidence for each, and finally using machine learning feature importance (XGBoost 2021) to ultimately decide the most important predictive characteristics. The next sections present exploratory data analysis.

1.2. Census / Geodemographic data

To investigate Census data as a driver of property price, we used data from NOMIS (NOMIS 2021). The statistics engaged are listed below, and all were taken at the MSOA (Middle Super Output Area), household level.

- Level 1 as Highest Qualification
- Level 4 (degree) as Highest Qualification
- Zero vehicles
- Three vehicles
- Average number bedrooms
- Number of lone parent households

Typically, Pearson's correlation coefficient is used to test a relationship between two numeric variables.

However, this statistic makes assumptions about normality of data, and the distribution of property prices is negatively skewed. Further, prices lack independence; nationally there exists strong geographic autocorrelation.

Instead, visualizations were used to describe relationships. Figure 1 shows the price distribution for neighbourhoods in the top 25% of Level 4 (i.e., degree level) education in blue, and the remaining 75% of properties in red. The figure suggests that neighborhoods with a higher level of degree education are associated with greater property prices.

Figure 1 Price distribution for levels of degree education

1.3. Geospatial analysis

Figure 2 shows a choropleth map of the median price for each local authority in England and Wales. This figure suggests that the closer to London, the greater the price, with some minor exceptions.

Figure 2 Median property price for local authorities

The challenge for us as model builders was to seek the optimal representation of geography as input to a machine learning model. One particularly useful spatially-oriented predictor was a simple scalar, the straight-line distance to Charing Cross – used as ‘kilometre zero’ when calculating distances from London.

1.4. Crime data

To test the hypothesis that crime affects house prices, data was taken from the Police’s data website (Police 2021) at the MSOA level.

Figure 5 Price distribution for levels of crime

Figure 5 shows the price distribution for properties in MSOAs in the top 25% of number of crimes per person, vs all other properties. Though there is some distinction between crime and price, this difference is slight, and there is much overlap, which is evident in the tail of both distributions.

The lack of strength in direct relationship between crime and price has been demonstrated in previous research (Whitworth 2012), indeed it may be that crime correlates with other characteristics (e.g., inequality) that better describe variation in house prices. This is an example of multicollinearity; whilst there appears to be some relationship between crime and price, the associated variation in property price is already better explained by other, correlated, characteristics of neighborhoods.

1.5. Temporal relationships

House prices vary over time, as evidenced in HM Land Registry 2021. Recently, prices surged, and the increase aligns with a stamp duty holiday implemented by the UK government in 2020 (Osborne 2021), however not all articles support that the stamp duty effect was causative (Judge, Shah, Odamtten 2021).

To explore this, a flag was created, true for properties sold during the stamp duty holiday and false otherwise. To adjust for spatial variation in prices, the difference before and after implementation was calculated for a range of postal areas in England and Wales, and selected results are shown in Figure 6. This suggests a price increase during the stamp duty holiday in the selected postal areas.

Figure 6 Median price for four postal areas, before and after stamp duty holiday

Model Results

A range of machine learning models were tested until a best set of input features were found. The first model used only data from the Price Paid Data, i.e., without additional open data. The subsequent models iteratively added open data sources until an optimal solution was reached.

The XGBoost algorithm was optimized by minimizing the RMSE (root mean squared error), but three additional metrics were collected during iterations. This was to maximise insight into the strengths and weaknesses of iterations; to provide transparency on areas of the target variable distribution where the model did and did not predict well. The additional metrics were Median Absolute Error (MAE), Adjusted R-Squared, and Mean Absolute Percentage Error. The results are shown in Table 2 for two iterations: the model using only the Price Paid Data, and the final model with open data.

Table 2 Model Results

Model	Adj R-squared	RMSE	MAE	MAPE (%)
Baseline	0.542	£206k	£38k	25.5%
Fully Tuned Open Data	0.843	£43k	£19k	11.4%

One important aspect of the final model is that its errors are linear and balanced. This can be seen in Figure 7, which shows the distribution of residuals (actual minus predicted) for the baseline and the final model. Not only are errors for the final model narrower in scope, but they are symmetrical about zero.

Figure 7 Error distribution for models

One of the implications of a well-balanced model is, when the total value of many properties is predicted, the error tends to zero. For example, if we take the total value of predictions from 500 randomly selected properties from the test set, and compare it with the actual total, it is very close. The same pattern also persists for selected geographic areas, and these results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Model Results – Many Properties

Sample	Sum predictions	Sum actual prices	% Difference
L postal area	1134411000	1131451970	0.2%
B postal area	3409919500	3418158733	-0.2%
SW postal area	1567689500	1581798844	-0.8%
500 randomly selected	127694985	128130740	0.3%

Conclusion

We created a machine learning model that predicts sale price for property sold in England and Wales. Despite heterogeneity in property price, the model still predicts a single property’s price to within 11.4%. Further, because the errors are balanced and symmetrical, when the total value of a group of properties is compared with the total value of predictions, the error is reduced to <1%.

We believe this model to be better than previous versions in the literature due to scope; by considering observations across both a large spatial feature space (i.e., nationally), and temporal feature space (over several years), the model can learn from variation that locally might seem idiosyncratic, but globally is more homogeneous.

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Biographies

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